

PROBLEMS IN TEACHING TECHNICAL SCIENCES

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Annotation: This article analyzes the main challenges in the teaching of technical sciences and proposes solutions to address them. Teaching technical sciences is a vital part of the national education system and directly influences a country's economic, technological, and scientific-technical development. Key issues include outdated curricula, a lack of practice-oriented education, obsolete technological equipment, insufficient teacher qualifications, and low student motivation. To address these issues, recommendations include modernizing curricula, developing practice-based education systems, equipping institutions with modern technologies, improving teacher qualifications, and introducing motivational systems for students.

Keywords: Teaching technical sciences, Modern technologies, Curricula, Practice-oriented education, Teacher qualifications, Student motivation, Innovative approaches, Education system development.

Introduction: In today's era of globalization and innovative development, teaching technical sciences is a critical component of the national education system. This field plays a vital role in ensuring the economic, technological, and scientific-technical progress of nations. Through the teaching of technical sciences, not only theoretical knowledge but also practical skills essential for industrial processes are developed. However, this field of education faces several challenges that need to be addressed, as they may lower the quality of education and limit graduates'

employability. This article comprehensively analyzes the key problems in the process of teaching technical sciences, their causes, and potential solutions.

Systematic Challenges in Teaching Technical Sciences.The process of teaching technical sciences is characterized by several systemic problems, detailed below:

Outdated Curricula:Many curricula and textbooks do not meet modern technological demands or align with industrial development trends. This hinders the formation of professionals capable of meeting market needs. Specifically, advanced innovations, digital technologies, and automation processes are insufficiently reflected in the curricula.

Lack of Practice-Oriented Education:Many educational institutions overly emphasize theory, leaving students unprepared for real-life practical situations. For example, weak collaboration with industrial enterprises results in difficulties for students in acquiring practical skills.

Obsolete Technological Equipment:Laboratories and practical training rooms in educational institutions are inadequately equipped with modern technologies. This deprives students of opportunities to familiarize themselves with evolving technologies in practice.

Teachers’ Qualifications and Pedagogical Approaches:Some educators lack practical experience with modern technologies, posing challenges to training students to meet global standards. Additionally, insufficient application of interactive and innovative pedagogical methods reduces the effectiveness of the educational process.

Low Student Motivation:Learning technical sciences requires high levels of intellectual and analytical skills from students. However, the lack of a motivational system to spark interest leads to reduced active participation in the learning process.

Recommendations for Addressing Problems in Teaching Technical Sciences.To address the issues mentioned above, the following measures are proposed:

Modernizing Curricula:Curricula for technical sciences should integrate modern technologies, digital platforms, and automation processes. It is essential to enhance textbooks and educational materials based on international experiences.

Implementing Practice-Based Education:Students should be involved in internships at industrial enterprises and trained through practical projects. Developing a dual education system to engage students in industrial processes during their studies is

also recommended. Upgrading Technological Infrastructure: Equipping laboratories and practical training rooms in educational institutions with modern equipment is crucial for preparing students for innovative processes. For instance, access to 3D printers, digital software, and automated systems should be expanded. Enhancing Teachers' Qualifications: Teachers should regularly participate in professional development courses and training. International exchange programs can be established to bring teachers' knowledge to a global level. Introducing Student Incentive Systems: To increase student interest, it is necessary to establish reward systems based on competitions, grants, and practical projects. Additionally, organizing meetings with successful professionals in the field can play a significant role in boosting motivation.

Conclusion

Teaching technical sciences is essential for the development of the education system and the technological progress of society. Addressing existing problems in this field requires adopting modern approaches. Reforms such as implementing practice-based education systems, modernizing laboratories, and enhancing teachers' qualifications will contribute to improving education quality. Moreover, fostering student motivation and interest in technical sciences can lead to the preparation of highly qualified specialists.

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